

FACETS OF AUDIO-VISUAL ROUGHNESS: FROM GRANULARITY TO SHARPNESS

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ABSTRACT

The salience of auditory roughness is demonstrated by its long-standing theoretical interest, dating back to Helmholtz nearly two centuries ago. Since then, psychoacousticians have proposed numerous models to predict perceived roughness, while neuroscientific evidence has highlighted its evolutionary role in signalling alarm and danger. Naturally, these properties are widely used in music as a vehicle for evoking tension or relaxation, a schema crucial for music appreciation. At the same time, roughness—originally a sensory loan from touch—features notable cross-modal associations commonly rooted in amplitude irregularities and fluctuations. Our approach proposes that auditory roughness may overlap with qualities such as granularity, sharpness, or noisiness. To test whether these concepts can be consistently distinguishable, even without relying on lexical descriptions, we designed and conducted a five-alternative forced-choice experiment. In this task, participants assigned 18 sound stimuli to one of four tailored visual analogues (granular, sharp, rough, and noisy) or to a ‘no image’ option. Our data analysis revealed an overall above-chance correspondence between sounds and images, justifying further investigation of acoustic predictors for each visual category. Our modelling suggests that *granularity* can be acoustically differentiated from *roughness* based on its concentration of energy at slower temporal modulations, as revealed by modulation power spectrum analysis. Additionally, Zwicker’s sharpness was positively associated with *granularity* and negatively with *roughness*. However, the acoustic trends for *sharpness* and *noisiness* were not statistically significant, indicating that future work should focus on fewer roughness variants and expand the sound stimulus set to reach more definitive conclusions.

1 Introduction

Roughness is a salient auditory quality and empirical evidence suggests that it is arguably the most universally agreed-upon semantic dimension of timbre across different linguistic groups and levels of musical expertise [1–4]. Auditory roughness is associated with feelings of unpleasantness, danger, and alarm [5–7], underscoring its ecolog-
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ical relevance. Unsurprisingly, music creators take advantage of this auditory property to evoke emotional states, particularly by reinforcing the tension-relaxation schema through sensory cues [8–11].

Roughness is alternatively referred to as ‘sensory’ or ‘auditory’ dissonance [12–14], in part to distinguish it from tonal dissonance. While auditory roughness does contribute to tonal dissonance [15], evidence suggests that dissonance perception is culture-dependent, whereas roughness perception remains consistent across cultures [16–19].

Given the prominence of roughness as an auditory dimension, it follows that various models have been developed to predict it (e.g., [13, 20–24]). Roughness arises from rapid amplitude fluctuations [22], which can either directly stem from temporal modulation or indirectly from the proximity of frequency components. The modulation frequencies responsible for producing roughness were initially identified within the 15–75 Hz range [25], but more recent studies have broadened this range, linking roughness to modulation energy between 30–150 Hz [4, 5].

Beyond audition, roughness is a prominent perceptual attribute in both tactile and visual perception [7]. Notably, the strong cross-modal associations around roughness have led some researchers to propose that it may even represent an amodal attribute [7]. In particular, recent evidence has increasingly supported cross-modal associations between auditory roughness and both visual and tactile roughness. Giannos et al. [26], for instance, conducted a cross-modal matching experiment demonstrating a correspondence between visual roughness and the dissonance of harmonic progressions. Similarly, vibrotactile and auditory roughness curves exhibited a close correspondence when generated from the summation of two sine waves with varying Δf [27].

While such findings support a close cross-modal association between the sensation of roughness in the auditory, visual, and tactile domains, it could be argued that roughness may encompass a number of facets. Such conceptual variations in the auditory domain may include *sharpness*, which can be seen as an antonym of *smoothness*. Positioned between auditory *brightness* and *roughness* [28], sharpness also contributes to auditory consonance alongside roughness [29]. *Granularity* is another quality used interchangeably with roughness [27, 30], rooted in irregularities and discontinuities within both auditory and visual domains. This concept is particularly relevant when describing certain textures in electroacoustic music [31]. Finally, *noisy* sonorities are often attributed rough qualities due to ran-

dom amplitude fluctuations [32, 33].

The empirical experiment presented in this work aimed to explore potential links between the aforementioned aspects of auditory and visual roughness. To this end, we designed and conducted a five-alternative forced-choice (5AFC) experiment in which the first four categories corresponded to specially drawn images representing *granularity*, *sharpness*, *roughness*, and *noisiness*, with the fifth category being ‘none of the above’. The first goal of the experiment was to investigate potential systematic associations between these visual categories and a set of audio stimuli characterised by varying degrees of roughness. The second goal, equally important, was to identify the acoustic characteristics that could predict the selection of these visual response categories. To achieve this, we extracted a number of audio features that have been linked to roughness or sharpness in previous research [4, 32] and used them as predictors in multinomial regression models. The hypothesis examined here is that different time scales of temporal modulations would be reflected in different image choices, e.g., faster and denser modulations associated with the noisy and sparser modulations with the granular image.

The following sections describe the experimental method and materials, then present the statistical analysis of the responses alongside the acoustic modelling. Finally, the paper concludes with a discussion of the findings and future directions.

2 Method

2.1 Visual categories

Four grayscale figures (Figure 1) were hand-drawn by the second author and refined based on feedback from the entire research team to visually depict the four variations of roughness discussed in the introduction: granularity, sharpness, roughness, and noisiness. *Granularity* was conveyed through particles of different shapes and sizes, as well as varying levels of density. *Sharpness* was represented by triangular, tooth-like forms with pointed edges. *Roughness*, by contrast, was visually expressed through lines with small jagged edges, whose varying angularity formed an irregular yet somewhat cohesive pattern. Finally, *noisiness* was illustrated using densely packed, variably shaped lines that sustained a sense of constant visual energy.

These four figures were used in a brief forced-choice experiment, in which 19 participants (12 female) selected the most appropriate semantic category (granular, sharp, rough, or noisy) for each figure. The results seem to confirm our hypothesis, albeit within the limiting context of a forced-choice protocol. Table 1 shows the corresponding contingency table. A Chi-square test of independence returned $\chi^2(9) = 94.53, p < 0.00001$. The effect size of the contingency table, measured by Cramér’s V ($V = 0.644$), suggests a strong association [34] between the semantic categories and the images. Figure 2 displays the significant standardised residuals, corrected using the False Discovery Rate (Benjamini-Hochberg) method. This correction

Figure 1. The four bespoke hand-drawn figures used in the 5-alternative forced-choice experiment to represent different facets of visual roughness.

reveals that image A was significantly assigned to granular, image B to sharp, image C to rough, and image D to noisy.

Table 1. Contingency table containing participant selections by semantic category for each image.

	Image A	Image B	Image C	Image D
Sharp	1	15	1	2
Rough	3	3	12	1
Noisy	1	1	3	14
Granular	14	0	3	2

Figure 2. Heatmap of standardised residuals from the Chi-square test of independence on the data from the four-alternative forced-choice experiment assessing semantic categorisation of each image. Significant matchings are highlighted after False Discovery Rate (Benjamini-Hochberg) correction.

2.2 Audio stimuli

Eighteen sound stimuli¹ were either synthesised or recorded by the second author to represent the range of auditory roughness variations described above. The set included mechanical sounds (e.g., car engine revving, fan noise), a natural soundscape (rain), various noises, grainy textures, a processed musical instrument (cello) and even one human vocalisation.

2.3 Participants

Forty-nine participants (mean age: 36.1 years, age range: 17 - 64 years, 24 female) took part in the current experiment. Musical expertise was not a prerequisite; therefore, our sample comprised both individuals with at least some musical training (18) and non-musicians (31), who were analysed together.

2.4 Experimental procedure

In a five-alternative forced-choice experiment, participants were asked to match each sound stimulus to one of four visual stimuli or select ‘none of the above’. Participants received no semantic cues or descriptive information about the image response categories to prevent bias in their decision-making process. The sound stimuli were presented in a randomised order to counterbalance potential order effects, and participants could listen to each sound as many times as needed before making a visual selection. Participants were advised to use headphones or good-quality monitors for audio playback. This experiment received ethical approval from the Aristotle University ethics board.

3 Results

3.1 Assessing the significance of sound-image associations

Initially, we aimed to assess whether responses associating the sound stimuli with the four visual categories exceeded chance levels, both as a whole and for individual sound stimuli. To this end, we performed a Chi-square test of independence on the contingency table of responses (Table 2), which revealed that the way sounds were categorised did not occur at random, but followed a consistent pattern, $\chi^2(68) = 430.32, p < 0.0001$. The effect size of the contingency table, measured by Cramér’s V ($V = 0.349$), suggests a moderate-to-strong association [34] between the two modalities.

At the individual level, Figure 3 illustrates the strength of associations between each sound and the five response categories (including the no-image option) in the forced-choice selection task. Subfigure 3a presents the significant uncorrected standardised residuals from the Chi-square test of independence, while Subfigure 3b shows the significant standardised residuals after False Discovery Rate (Benjamini-Hochberg) correction, which enhances sensitivity to meaningful relationships while controlling false

Table 2. Contingency table of image assignments (counts).

	granular	sharp	rough	noise	no image
s1	8	19	8	9	5
s2	26	4	4	12	3
s3	0	25	9	6	9
s4	1	13	17	13	5
s5	3	22	4	9	11
s6	7	10	11	15	6
s7	3	22	3	7	14
s8	5	17	15	0	12
s9	9	9	13	10	8
s10	18	1	22	8	0
s11	7	12	12	13	5
s12	7	8	3	19	12
s13	9	8	22	6	4
s14	38	3	4	0	4
s15	24	2	15	6	2
s16	2	22	6	14	5
s17	8	7	19	11	4
s18	0	16	11	4	18

discoveries. The uncorrected coefficients reveal 13 out of 18 significant associations, while the stricter corrected coefficients still indicate significant associations for 11 out of 18 sounds with one of the images.

3.2 Modelling audio-visual correspondences through audio features

Having confirmed a systematic matching between sounds and images, we proceeded to examine how auditory features influence visual selections. To this end, we computed conditional probabilities reflecting the likelihood of each visual category being chosen given a specific sound stimulus, $P(\text{Visual} | \text{Auditory})$. Responses from the five-alternative forced-choice task were aggregated into an 18×5 contingency table, capturing the distribution of selections across conditions. A multinomial regression was then performed on this contingency structure to assess the extent to which auditory dimensions systematically influenced visual choices.

The modelling explored five features that have been linked with auditory roughness and sharpness. The first two consisted of auditory roughness and sharpness based on the work by Fastl & Zwicker [32] and computed using the MATLAB functions `acousticRoughness` and `acousticSharpness`. The remaining three were based on attributes of the Modulation Power Spectrum (MPS), known to predict auditory roughness [4, 5]. The MPS is the 2D-Fourier transform of a spectrogram that quantifies the distribution of modulation energy across the temporal and spectral dimensions. In this study, the 2D Fourier transform was applied to a loudness spectrogram estimated using MATLAB’s `specificLoudness` function, which implements Zwicker’s method for loudness estimation (ISO 532-1) [32], rather than a spectrogram derived from a standard Fourier transform. Specifically, the following three MPS-derived features were examined: the mean energy within the 30–150 Hz range of the temporal modulation axis [4], the peak modulation frequency within this range, and the

¹ The sound stimulus set can be accessed at [GitHub](#).

Figure 3. Heatmap of the standardised residuals from the Chi-square test of independence, with blue indicating negative values and yellow representing positive values, where non-significant values are shown in white. (a) Significant matchings for the uncorrected standardised residuals. (b) Significant matchings after False Discovery Rate (Benjamini-Hochberg) correction.

spectral centroid of the 1–29 Hz region.

A multinomial regression model was then employed to predict image choice probabilities through the audio features. To enhance interpretability, the predictors were transformed using a signed logarithmic function. Specifically, the transformation $x = \text{sign}(x) \cdot \log(1+|x|)$ was used to manage differences in scale while preserving the directional information. This approach substantially reduced skewness and brought the data distribution closer to normality, improving the stability and interpretability of regression coefficients. Standardisation (z-scoring) was subsequently performed to ensure comparability across features. Model evaluation relied on log-likelihood-based metrics, including McFadden’s R^2 and Nagelkerke’s R^2 , to assess explanatory power. Predictions were made in terms of probability distributions over image choices rather than discrete classifications, allowing for a more nuanced interpretation of the relationship between predictors and response probabilities.

Table 3 presents the beta coefficients of the selected multinomial regression model. Several pairwise combinations of the five examined descriptors resulted in significant models, with the final choice of Zwicker’s sharpness and MPS roughness (i.e., the mean energy within the 30–150 Hz range of temporal modulation frequencies) yielding the highest McFadden’s R^2 (0.3002). The model fit was moderately strong, with a log-likelihood of -19.88 and pseudo R^2 values of McFadden’s $R^2 = 0.3002$ and Nagelkerke’s $R^2 = 0.6395$ —suggesting that the model explains a substantial portion of the variance in participants’ choices. The prediction accuracy (of the most likely category) reached 72.22%, well above the chance level of 25%. However, the log loss of 8.88 indicates that while the model often assigned the highest probability to the most probable category, its predictions were not made with

Table 3. Multinomial regression results predicting the selection of different image categories (vs. no-image) based on acoustic features. The sign and magnitude of the beta coefficients indicate how the probability of selecting a given category is influenced by each feature, accompanied by 95% confidence intervals and significance levels. Model fit: Log-Likelihood (\mathcal{L}) = -19.88 ; McFadden’s $R^2 = 0.3002$, Nagelkerke’s $R^2 = 0.6395$; Prediction Accuracy = 72.22%; Log Loss = 8.88. These metrics reflect the model’s goodness-of-fit, classification performance, and uncertainty in predictions. Likelihood Ratio Test (LRT) p-values: Zwicker’s sharpness = 0.0000, MPS roughness = 0.0000, indicating that both predictors are statistically significant.

Predictors	Betas	p-Value	95% CI
Cat. 1: [Granular]			
Intercept	-150.7	<.0001	[-179.2, -122.3]
Zwicker’s sharpness	129.9	<.0001	[106.5, 153.4]
MPS roughness	-69.3	<.0001	[-84.77, -53.93]
Cat. 2: [Sharp]			
Intercept	2.3	.1546	[-0.87, 5.47]
Zwicker’s sharpness	1.5	.5586	[-3.45, 6.39]
MPS roughness	0.8	.6081	[-2.26, 3.86]
Cat. 3: [Rough]			
Intercept	-10.6	.0378	[-20.58, -0.60]
Zwicker’s sharpness	-12.4	.0154	[-22.50, -2.37]
MPS roughness	12.1	.0120	[2.66, 21.54]
Cat. 4: [Noisy]			
Intercept	-1.5	.6221	[-7.60, 4.54]
Zwicker’s sharpness	4.7	.1731	[-2.07, 11.54]
MPS roughness	-2.6	.2542	[-7.15, 1.89]

high confidence. This gap highlights a potential calibration issue, which would not be unexpected given the small

dataset size and observed class imbalances (see Table 2). On the other hand, the Likelihood Ratio Test (LRT) p -values for Zwicker’s sharpness and MPS roughness were both < 0.001 , confirming that both predictors significantly contribute to the model. Together, these metrics indicate that the resulting model provides a satisfactory fit to the data and captures meaningful relationships between auditory features and visual category selection.

The model also demonstrated meaningful interpretability, as many of the betas were statistically significant. The beta coefficients of Table 3 indicate how Zwicker’s sharpness and MPS roughness influence the likelihood of selecting a given image category compared to the reference category (no-image). According to the model, the likelihood of selecting the *granular* image strongly increases with higher auditory sharpness and lower MPS roughness. Conversely, higher MPS roughness makes the selection of the *rough* image more likely, whereas this tendency is reversed for auditory sharpness. Positive tendencies between Zwicker’s sharpness and the *sharp* and *noisy* images are also observed, though they do not reach statistical significance. MPS roughness exhibits a weak positive relationship with the *sharp* image and a weak negative relationship with the *noisy* image, but neither effect is statistically significant.

4 Discussion

Data analysis of the five-alternative forced-choice experiment, in which sounds served as stimuli and images as response categories, revealed an overall above-chance correspondence between sounds and images. More specifically, this pattern held in more than half of the cases even after False Discovery Rate correction. This suggests that participants were often able to make systematic audio-visual associations, though not consistently in all cases. The granular and sharp visual categories had the highest number of significant associations (4), followed by rough (1 on its own and 1 shared with granular), and finally noisy, with only a single (1) significant association.

At this point it is worth noting that, although our hypothesis about the semantic associations of the response images was supported by a small four-alternative forced-choice experiment including the terms sharp, rough, granular, and noisy (see Figure 2), it is possible that the bounded nature of that validation leaves room for alternative interpretations of the images in the broader context of the main cross-modal matching experiment. For example, it is plausible that the curved lines in the noisy image may have discouraged participants from associating it with the noisy and rough timbres of our stimulus set, as its only statistically significant match (s12) was a tone—likely one of the least rough and noisy in the set. The no-image category featured one unique significant match (s18) and another one shared with sharp (s7). Interestingly, s18 was the only stimulus in the set originating from a human source (i.e., a rough vocalisation).

While the systematic differentiation between related images and sounds is an interesting finding in itself, the second goal of this work was to provide insight into the acous-

tic properties of the sounds that drive the observed cross-modal effects. Although the high number of response categories (5) relative to stimuli (18) limited the inclusion of multiple features in the models (due to overfitting), modelling with a few key audio descriptors still identified trends worth discussing.

The optimal multinomial regression model attributed an acoustic profile to each of the four images, although not all predictors yielded significant beta values. Consistent with previous literature, higher MPS roughness—defined as the mean temporal modulation energy within the 30–150 Hz region of the modulation power spectrum—increased the likelihood of selecting the rough image over the no-image category ($\beta = 12.1$). At the same time, and in line with our initial hypothesis, granular became more likely as MPS roughness decreased ($\beta = -69.3$), suggesting that the faster fluctuations associated with roughness undermine the perception of granularity. In contrast, Zwicker’s sharpness positively influenced the likelihood of selecting the granular category ($\beta = 129.9$) and negatively influenced the selection of the rough category ($\beta = -12.43$). The sharp and noisy response categories did not show statistically significant beta values for the two predictors used. However, a positive trend was observed between both Zwicker’s sharpness and MPS roughness and the sharp response category. The noisy response category was not acoustically distinct from granular, showing a positive trend with Zwicker’s sharpness and a negative trend with MPS roughness.

The preliminary evidence presented in this work regarding the visual representation of auditory roughness is encouraging, suggesting that such a mapping is possible but warrants more detailed investigation. Future work should focus on fewer visual roughness categories (e.g., a 2AFC protocol or even an active manipulation of a single visual variable) and a larger number of sound stimuli to enable stronger acoustic predictions of roughness facets. In such a scenario, a broader range of roughness models, coupled with a more in-depth exploration of features derived from the modulation power spectrum, could provide more robust insights into the acoustic correlates of roughness subtleties.

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